

Generation of an Equilibrium Core Configuration for a Small Boiling Water Reactor Similar to the BWRX-300

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ABSTRACT

The BWRX-300 is a small boiling water reactor (SBWR) that relies on natural circulation for cooling and targets an extended cycle length of 18-24 months. It is important to understand how these reactors operate in a variety of operating conditions and transients, so this work aims to develop a comprehensive neutronics model of the BWRX using public domain information. The model uses the GE14 fuel assembly with the average enrichment increased to 4% to achieve the desired cycle length. A shuffle pattern and control rod pattern (CRP) were developed to ensure criticality and even burnup throughout the cycle length. The thermal limits were evaluated by the linear heat generation rate (LHGR) and critical power ratio (CPR). The maximum LHGR was found to be well below the safety limit set forth by GE, with a value of 8.98 kW/ft. The MCPR has a minimum of 1.37, which is slightly below the operational limit but well above the safety limit. The average discharge burnup for the core was found to be 43.16 GWd/MTU, which is below the limit set for the BWRX of 45 GWd/MTU. The lead pin discharge burnup was calculated to be 61.89 GWd/MTU, which is also below the conservative limit set in the design of 63 GWd/MTU. This neutronics model was designed to be a representative model of the BWRX-300 to allow for future analysis of the core at various operation conditions.

Keywords: SBWR, BWRX, Equilibrium, Core Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

As part of the new generation of nuclear energy, it is imperative to understand how small modular boiling water reactors (SBWRs) operate and behave under a variety of conditions. One of the leading designs for this reactor type is the BWRX-300 developed by GE-Hitachi. The BWRX-300 is a 300 MWe water-cooled, natural circulation small modular reactor that targets an 18-24 month fuel cycle [1]. This design improves upon prior reactors with simplified operation and passive safety systems. This is mainly due to its incorporation of inherent safety through the use of gravity and natural circulation in its design. The BWRX is currently being built, but this work aims to build a public domain assessment of its performance. Common challenges for designing these reactors are designing a fuel cycle for the reduced size and increased cycle length and the neutronic effects that result from the natural circulation and two-phase flow. In this study, core analysis was performed to design an equilibrium core configuration for the BWRX to be used for future work. Work has been done to study these reactors before [2], where an equilibrium core was developed to analyze the key reactor parameters and their adherence to safety limits. This work aims to develop an open-source, equilibrium core for the BWRX using codes developed by the NRC. The design process for the model follows the conventional two-step procedure, specifically utilizing POLARIS as the lattice physics calculation tool [3] and PARCS as the whole core analysis tool. This method has been well verified for analyzing BWRs [4]. This paper will outline the work done to generate the configuration as well as evaluate it using the linear heat generation rate (LHGR) and critical power ratio (CPR).

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2. CORE DESIGN

2.1. GE-14 Fuel Assembly Description

The BWRX-300 design uses a 240 assembly core configuration consisting of the GNF2 fuel bundle [1]. This is used for low hydraulic resistance which benefits the natural circulation of the reactor. For this work, the GE-14 fuel assembly was used instead due to a lack of public information describing the GNF2 bundle. The GE-14 bundle is very similar in design as both are 10x10 lattices consisting of both full and partial length fuel rods and has been used in place of the GNF2 in other work performing core analysis for BWRs [5]. There are also similarities in the burnable poison loading between the two.

The GE-14 fuel assembly design used was taken from the BWR benchmark problems developed by ORNL, which was developed through the compiling of several different data sources [6]. There are 92 fuel pins and two large water rods in each bundle, all surrounded by a zirconium alloy box. In each lattice, 14 of the fuel pins are partial length with an active length of 2.134m, and the remaining are full length rods with an active length of 3.81m. Seven different lattice types were used when modeling the GE-14, including variations in enrichment, poison loading, and partial rod presence. There are grid spacers present in the GE-14, but these were not modeled explicitly. Instead, the spacers mass and material were homogenized into the coolant to capture the overall effect on the neutronics. Figure 1 shows the axial view of the different lattices in the fuel assembly and a radial view of the lattice.

(a) Axial view of lattice.

(b) Radial view of lattice with all rods present.

Figure 1. Full schematic of lattice types in GE-14 fuel assembly. All dimensions are shown in cm.

The assembly design from the ORNL progression problems had an average enrichment of 3.4% and a maximum pin enrichment of 4.95% [6]. However, this enrichment was not high enough to achieve criticality for the target 24-month cycle, as is the target for the BWRX operating cycle. The average enrichment was increased to 4% to extend the fuel life cycle. The maximum pin enrichment remained below 5%, and the lower enriched pins were increased according to work done to model fuels for higher burnup LWR cores by increasing the lower enriched pins to target an extended fuel cycle [7].

2.2. Reactor Design

The core was designed according to parameters available in open literature. This includes values used for both the neutronics and thermal-hydraulics calculations. These are listed in Table I.

There are control blades located throughout the core, grouping sets of four neighboring assemblies. Only a small portion of these are used during typical core operation, with the rest reserved for shutdown procedure. Figure 2 shows a quarter symmetric model of the southwest quadrant of the core with the

Table I. Parameters used for full core modeling from open literature.

Parameter	Value
Single Core Thermal Power	870 MWth
Nominal Coolant Flow Rate	1827 kg/s*
Number of Fuel "Units"	240
Core Inlet Temperature	270C
Core Outlet Temperature	287C
Core Operating Pressure	7.2 MPa
Core Discharge Burnup	49.5 GWd/MTU

three control banks actively used during operation shown and labeled.

Figure 2. Quarter symmetric representation of the core with control banks marked.

2.3. Limiting Design Criteria

The following constraints were applied to the design process and used to determine the final equilibrium core configuration.

- **Fuel cycle criticality.** The core must maintain near criticality for the entire duration of the fuel cycle. Specifically, the multiplication factor must remain within 500 pcm of criticality.
- **Core discharge burnup.** The average core discharge burnup has a limit of 49.5GWd/MTU [1].
- **Lead pin discharge.** For the extended fuel cycle cores, the US limit is 70 GWd/MTU, but this work targeted a more conservative limit set by GE of 63 GWd/MTU [1].
- **Maximum Linear heat generation rate (MLHGR).** While specific thermal limits have not been published for the GE-14, GE has published limits for their other fuel types. The limit for this work has been set at 14.4 kW/ft, as this limit is for 9x9 fuel lattices and should be a conservative estimate for the 10x10 lattices in the GE-14 [8].
- **Minimum critical power ratio (MCPR).** Using limits for other GE fuel assemblies, the MCPR has a limit of 1.07 for safety, and an operational limit of 1.44 to account for abnormal transients [8].

3. METHODS

3.1. Lattice Cross Section Generation with POLARIS

Developed at Oak Ridge National Laboratory, the POLARIS package within SCALE was used to generate the cross section data for the GE-14 bundle needed for the later full core analysis. A 2D model was built for each lattice type present, and cross sections were generated at state points spanning the possible operating conditions during transients in the BWRX. This includes fuel temperatures, control blade presence, and void fraction. This void fractions are crucial to capture when modeling natural circulation BWRs due to the complex nature of flow that results from their operation. Examples of lattices with both the partial rods present and missing modeled for the GE-14 fuel assembly are shown in Figure 3.

(a) 10x10 lattice with all rods present.

(b) 10x10 lattice with partial rods missing.

Figure 3. Two lattices modeled for the GE-14 fuel assembly using POLARIS.

3.2. Full-Core Modeling with PARCS

The Purdue Advance Reactor Core Simulator (PARCS) code is a three dimensional, diffusion based reactor core simulator and was used in this work to perform the full core analysis [9]. GenPMAXS was first used to convert the cross sections output by POLARIS into a format usable by PARCS [9]. This handles the branch structure as well as assembly discontinuity factors, pin power factors, and xenon cross sections. For the purpose of developing the model, it was built according to quarter core, rotational symmetry to reduce calculation time and streamline the process. PARCS also has depletion calculation capabilities, and this allowed for calculating multiple cycles to converge on the equilibrium core design. This feature of PARCS handles the fuel shuffling that happens between fuel cycles, and this was used to develop the shuffle pattern for the equilibrium core.

For this work, the internal TH code PATHS was used to solve for the thermal hydraulic conditions resulting from two-phase flow, as the PARCS/PATHS suite has been verified for modeling complex BWR fuel assembly geometries [10]. The thermal-hydraulic parameters reported in Table I were used as inputs for PATHS, but it should be noted that the input flow rate used was taken to be 90% of the reported value to account for bypass flow. This assumption enforces consistency with corresponding TH models of the BWRX-300.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Cycle Designs

The resulting core configuration designed for the BWRX-300 consists of three batches of fuel, all equal in size. Initially, a fully fresh fuel model was built in PARCS, with the shuffle map and control rod pattern

(CRP) programmed for the multi-cycle analysis. These were adjusted to achieve criticality over the desired fuel cycle length and minimize any power peaking for the equilibrium configuration. As stated prior, the average enrichment for the fuel assembly was increased to 4% to achieve the 24 month cycle. The shuffle map follows the ring of fire approach and places the twice-burned fuel assemblies around the periphery of the core and in a ring in the center to reduce radial leakage and minimize peaking in the center. The resulting shuffle map for the core is shown in Figure 4a, where the fresh fuel is indicated by blue squares with negative one values. Once- and twice-burned fuel are shown in yellow and red respectively, with the coordinates of the assembly's last location displayed. The columns are designated letters A-I and the rows are 1-9, with A1 being the center assembly. Figure 4b shows the CRP used for the equilibrium core, with the banks corresponding to those seen in Figure 2.

(a) Shuffle map for the equilibrium core, with the three batches of fuel designated in different colors.

(b) Control rod pattern (CPR) for the equilibrium core, showing all three batches percent removed from core.

Figure 4. Shuffle map and CRP for equilibrium core in multi-cycle search.

4.2. Core Power Distributions

The assembly-wise relative power distributions at the beginning (BOC) and end of cycle (EOC) for the equilibrium core are shown in Figure 5. The loading pattern is able to reduce the power peaking below limits, as will be discussed with the thermal limits later.

There is a large power bias towards the center of the core, but the presence of twice-burned fuel keeps the peaking from being too strong here. The axial power profile at the beginning and end of cycle are shown in Figure 6. The strong axial peaking in the bottom half of the core results from the control rods being used to offset the axially varying flux from the top half of the core voiding. The control blades begin fully inserted to balance the higher amount of uranium in the bottom half of the assemblies. As the blades are withdrawn and the burnable poisons burn out, the flux increases and shifts to a peak in the bottom half of the core, but the core still remains within safety limits.

The LHGR and CPR were chosen as the main criteria for the power peaking of the core. Limits on the LHGR are set to minimize strain on the fuel cladding, as fuel expansion from high power and temperature can lead to cracking. This was calculated using the 3D pin power factors output from PARCS to find the maximum pin power for each assembly, and that was simply divided by the rod length, dependent on if it is a partial or full length fuel pin. The MLHGR at each step of the cycle was calculated to ensure that each core configuration remains below its limit for the entirety of the cycle. The limit set on the CPR is to protect against fuel damage caused by loss of nuclear boiling. The MCPR was calculated by finding the assembly power required to cause the departure from nucleate boiling

(a) BOC power distribution (equilibrium).

(b) EOC power distribution (equilibrium).

Figure 5. Relative power distributions for the beginning and end of cycle for the equilibrium core.

Figure 6. Axial power profile for the equilibrium core at beginning and end of cycle.

ratio (DNBR) to become unity for each rod [11]. The DNBR was calculated using predicted critical heat fluxes found from the Groeneveld look up table [12], and the CPR was determined as the ratio between the critical and experimental powers. The minimum value for the CPR found will represent the assembly closest to transition boiling. Thus, the MCPR and MLHGR were found at each step in the desired cycle length to ensure that the power peaking in the core remain within the designated limits. Figure 7 displays the MLHGR and MCPR over the full cycle for the equilibrium core.

It can be seen that the MLHGR remains well below its limit for the entire cycle, with a maximum value of 8.98 kW/ft. The MCPR does fall below the limit at the BOC, with a minimum of 1.37. However, this only occurs at the first time step and is slightly below the operational limit. The MCPR does remain well above the safety limit for the entirety of the cycle, and the limits being compared against are for other assembly types (GNF2) and are representative for the assembly types being modeled [8]. The Groeneveld is a conservative correlation as well compared to the more model specific correlations that would be used by vendors to set limits. As a result, this core is accepted despite violating the operational limit slightly.

(a) MLHGR over the entire cycle for the equilibrium core.

(b) MCPR over the entire cycle for the equilibrium core.

Figure 7. Thermal limits for the equilibrium core over the desired cycle length.

4.3. Burnup limits

Figure 8 shows the burnup distributions at the beginning and end of cycle for the equilibrium configuration.

(a) BOC burnup distribution [GWD/MTU].

(b) EOC burnup distribution [GWD/MTU].

Figure 8. Burnup distributions for the beginning and end of cycle for the equilibrium core.

The core average discharge is 43.16 GWd/MTU, which is well below the set limit of 49.5. The assembly discharge burnup is relatively uniform across the core, with most falling between 40-50 GWd/MTU. Not shown in the figure is the lead pin discharge burnup, this was calculated from the PARCS output to be 61.89 GWd/MTU and accounts for heavy metal and assembly power fraction effects. This value is also below the set limit reported earlier. The most limiting assemblies for the core average and lead pin burnup are the three twice-burned assemblies surrounding the center of the core, as they are surrounded entirely by fresh assemblies.

5. CONCLUSIONS

An equilibrium core configuration was developed for the BWRX-300. This design utilized the GE-14 fuel assembly in the modeling process with the enrichment increased to an average of 4% while still

maintaining a maximum pin enrichment below 5% to reach the desired 24 month fuel cycle length. The core designs were able to meet the standards set by the initial core description. The power distribution for a BWR is limited by the resulting thermal behavior. For this work, the limiting LHGR was set at 14 kW/ft, and the core was well below this limit for the entirety of the fuel cycle, with maximum values of 8.98 and 1.37 for the MLHGR and MCPR respectively. The core discharge burnup was found to be 43.16 GWd/MTU, which is well below the set limit of 49.5 GWd/MTU. Likewise, the pin discharge burnup was calculated to be 61.89 GWd/MTU, and this value is also below the conservative limit set in the design of 63 GWd/MTU. For future work, the equilibrium core designed in this work will be coupled to a thermal hydraulics code like TRACE and used to analyze flow instabilities resulting from different operating conditions.

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